

FLOW STATE OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL IN THE
FORGING DIE DURING THE MOLDING PROCESS

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The molding process using the closed die contributes to the mass production technology for the composite materials. Though BMC (Bulk Molding Compound) and SMC (Sheet Molding Compound) have been developed for the process, it seems that there is some margin for improvement to obtain the success. One of the possible troubles in this process is that in the products the surface cavity is produced at the opposite side against the high convex part with thin wall (a fin). Another trouble is that the brittle weakness is produced in the bottom of the fin portion.

The purpose of this paper is to find the basic concept on the flow state during the molding process and to obtain the fundamental data necessary for the design of geometrical dimension of the die. For this aim, the numerical analyzing method should be established for the flow of the composite materials. In order to do this, numerical solutions computed for the idealized models were compared with experimental results so that the reasonable model was obtained.

Taking into consideration the difference between the fluid resistance in normal and parallel directions to the flow based on heterogeneity of the materials including reinforcements, the flow of BMC was calculated as anisotropic pseudo-plastic material flow using the finite element method. The flow state of BMC as the composite materials was compared with that of plasticine which shows the homogeneous isotropic behavior. The result was obtained that the characteristics of actual flow state can well be explained the numerical solutions derived for the isotropy and anisotropy.

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Introduction

Composite materials, such as glass fiber reinforced plastics (FRP), are now widely used in various industrial fields, e.g. automobile parts, electric appliance etc. As their utilization become wide, reinforcements for a mass production of the material and for its mechanization are increasing.

In this connection, by the development of SMC and BMC, much attention has been paid on the employment of a matched metal die molding process which are generally used in metal forming, where the bulk forming technique is applied to the composite materials with the temperature control of the materials. However, the process employed for the composite materials encounters the same difficulties with those known for the process of metallic products such as a formation of shrinkage cavity which very much impairs the value of products.

The difference in the above nature for the metallic products and composite materials is considered to be due to the fact that, while the metals are of homogeneous nature, the inclusion of reinforcements in the composite materials results in their heterogeneous nature and produces the anisotropy in the flow caused by the fiber orientation.

In the present paper, in an attempt to establish the method of numerical analysis for the flow properties of composite materials and to obtain the fundamental data to design the geometrical dimensions of die for the composite materials with the dispersed reinforcements, a comparison has been made on the experimental results and the numerical results that are calculated for the idealized model of the characteristic material flow.

Governing Equations and Formulations

In our earlier study the plastic flow of metal was found to be successfully analyzed by using the equations of homogeneous isotropic pseudo-plastic fluid as governing equations. However, it is assumed that the flow state of the composite materials can not be explained by these equations, since they are not isotropic as metal and include fibrous reinforcements. Therefore, on an assumption that in the case of the flow of composite materials the fiber orientation yields different fluid resistance in normal and parallel directions to the flow, the homogeneous orthotropic pseudo-plastic equations were derived and used as governing equations to analyze their flow state. The method of weighted residuals (a Galerkin formulation) was used to solve the derived equations.

Derivation of the Homogeneous Orthotropic Pseudo-Plastic Equations

The following motion and continuity equations for steady, incompressible and two-dimensional viscous fluid flow with non-body force are used as basic equations. These equations are written,

$$\rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\rho u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \tau_{yy}}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where u and v are the velocity components in x and y directions respectively and ρ is the density.

Here, it is assumed that the flow of the composite materials is non-Newtonian flow, especially the flow which obeys n power law ($n < 1$) in the relation between stress and strain-rate, as follows,

$$\sigma_v = K \cdot (\dot{\epsilon}_v)^n = K \cdot (\dot{\epsilon}_v)^{n-1} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_v, \quad (4)$$

where σ_v is uni-axial equivalent stress, $\dot{\epsilon}_v$ is uni-axial equivalent strain-rate, n is power exponent and K is the material constant.

On the other hand, the relation between stress and strain-rate in the case of the pseudo-plastic flow can be written,

$$\sigma_v = 3 \cdot \mu(J_2) \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_v, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\epsilon}_v &= \sqrt{4 \cdot J_2 / 3}, \\ 4J_2 &= 2\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right)^2, \end{aligned}$$

(for the case of plain strain)

and viscosity coefficient μ is a function of only the second invariant J_2 .

Comparing Eq. (4) with Eq. (5)

$$3 \cdot \mu(J_2) = K \cdot (\dot{\epsilon}_v)^{n-1} = K \cdot (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}.$$

Therefore,

$$\mu(J_2) = \frac{K}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}. \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, for the purpose of the consideration to the characteristic flow of the composite materials, Eq. (6) with the directional properties is transformed and it can be written as,

$$\mu_x(J_2) = \frac{K_x}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mu_y(J_2) = \frac{K_y}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}, \quad (8)$$

where K_x and K_y are pseudo-plastic viscosity in x and y directions respectively.

So, the constitutive equations for the orthotropic pseudo-plastic fluid flow can be written,

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{xx} = 2\mu_x \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - p & (9) \\ \tau_{xy} = \tau_{yx} = \mu_y \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \mu_x \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} & (10) \\ \tau_{yy} = 2\mu_y \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - p & (11) \end{cases}$$

Consequently, the orthotropic pseudo-plastic equations are given by the substitution Eq.(7) and Eq.(8) to Eq.(1) and Eq.(2) and by considering the negligible terms and they can be written,

$$\rho u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \mu_x (J_2) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\rho u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \rho v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} - \mu_y (J_2) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) = 0, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\mu_x (J_2) = \frac{K_x}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}, \quad \mu_y = \frac{K_y}{3} (\sqrt{4J_2/3})^{n-1}$$

$$4J_2 = 2\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + 2\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2.$$

Finite Element Formulations of the Pseudo-Plastic Equations

The method of weighted residual of Galerkin and the Newton-Raphson method are used to solve the non-linear partial differential equations (12)-(14), as it seems to be extremely difficult to solve them by exact analytical methods. Here, Eq.(12)- Eq.(14) are rearranged to Eq.(15)- Eq.(17),

$$Q(u, v, p) = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$R(u, v, p) = 0, \quad (16)$$

$$S(u, v, p) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Therefore, the formulation is

$$\int_V [W]^T \{ [G]^n \{ \Delta \phi \} + \{ f \}^n \} dV = \{ 0 \}, \quad (18)$$

$$\{\phi\} = \{u, v, p\}^T, \{\Delta\phi\} = \{\phi\}^{n+1} - \{\phi\}^n, \{f\}^n = \{Q^n, R^n, S^n\}^T,$$

$$\{\Delta\phi\} = [W] \{\Delta\Phi\} = [W_i, W_j, \dots, W_k] \{\Delta\Phi\},$$

where n is iterative step number, $[G]^n$ is Jacobian, $[W]$ is shape function or weighting function, $\{\Delta\Phi\}$ is nodal quantities, i, j, \dots, k are nodal numbers. When $[K]^n$ and $\{F\}^n$ are denoted, after applying Green's theorem, as follows,

$$[K]^n = \int_V [W]^T [G]^n [W] dV, \quad \{F\}^n = \int_V [W]^T \{f\}^n dV.$$

Eq.(18) is

$$[K]^n \{\Phi^{n+1} - \Phi^n\} + \{F\}^n = \{0\} \quad (19)$$

In Eq.(19), until $\{\Phi\}$ converges sufficiently, the calculation is repeated.

Numerical Results

To simplify the analysis of actual flow showing very complex state, a conversion of the actual three-dimensional and unsteady material flow into the two-dimensional and steady fluid flow was made. For the purpose of discussing the condition of troubles such as a shrinkage and a decline of the strength that occur during the process, a part of the ribbed boss where the dimensions in size and fillet arc are changeable was chosen as a model system for the shape of the canal.

As shown in Figs. 1 to 3, the finite element models for such a canal were constructed by assuming triangular elements with six nodes. The canal given in Fig. 1 was used to analyze the initial flow state in the molding process. The line AE in the figure is the symmetrical axis, AB is the surface of the punch, BCD is the inner surface of the die and DE is the entrance into the rib, respectively. The boundary conditions for this model are as follows; $v_y = 0.3$ mm/s (the velocity of the press stroke) on the line AB, a free surface condition on the line ED (the entrance into the rib) and a non-frictional condition along the wall boundary. For the analysis, the entrance condition of the rib canal without the wall was supposed as the free surface condition on the line ED. Although the conditions thus supposed does not correspond to the actual state, the initial flow state during the molding process can well be estimated by this simplification.

For more strict considerations of the actual state, the condition of the canal with the rib wall was supposed for the same canal with the corner radius of the die, $R_f = 0$ mm as shown in Fig. 2. In this case, the boundary condition for the free surface is on the line EF (see Fig. 2), while the remaining two boundary conditions for the velocity of the press stroke and for the non-frictional condition along the wall boundary are same with those employed for the initial flow state given above. In addition, the canal with $R_f \neq 0$ shown in Fig. 3 was used to investigate the effect of the corner radius of the die.

In Figs. 4 to 10, the flow states given as the velocity vectors which were determined from the numerical solutions are shown. In Figs. 4 to 6, the initial flow states during the molding process are also shown.

Fig. 1 - Finite element model for the analysis of the initial flow state.

Fig. 2 - Finite element model taking into consideration of rib wall.

Fig. 3 - Finite element model for the investigation of corner condition.

Fig. 4 shows the isotropic flow state, where the material constants are given as those of plasticine being the pseudo-plastic viscosity ($K_y = K_x$) of 0.018 Kg.s/mm² and the power exponent (n) of 0.08. It appears that the flow is comparatively gentle and tends to proceed to the axis of symmetry around the entrance into the rib canal.

Figs. 5 and 6 show the anisotropic flow states, where the ratio of the material constant, K_y/K_x , is 2.0 and 3.0, respectively. These data indicate that the flow state results in the meander through the corner into the rib. This is presumably due to the anisotropic nature of the flow. The tendency to produce such a meander becomes stronger as the ratio of the material constant, K_y/K_x , increases.

In Figs. 7 to 10 the flow states obtained for the models with additional condition for the rib part (Figs. 2 and 3) are given. From these figures it is obvious that, while the isotropic flow (Figs. 7 and 9) is gentle, the anisotropic flow (Figs. 8 and 10), though it is still gentle, has a tendency to flow slightly along the horizontal direction in the upper part surrounding the symmetric interface of the rib inlet. The latter has also a tendency of turbulent flow around the corner fillet of die as shown in fig. 10.

Fig. 4 - Velocity vectors calculated for the initial flow state in the case of isotropic flow ($K_y = K_x$).

Fig. 5 - Velocity vectors calculated for the initial flow state in the case of anisotropic flow ($K_y/K_x = 2.0$).

Fig. 6 - Velocity vectors calculated for the initial flow state in the case of anisotropic flow ($K_y/K_x = 3.0$).

Fig. 7 - Velocity vectors calculated for the canal with ribbed boss in the case of isotropic flow ($K_y = K_x$).

Fig. 8 - Velocity vectors calculated for the canal with ribbed boss in the case of anisotropic flow ($K_y/K_x = 3.0$).

Fig. 9 - Velocity vectors calculated to consider the effect of corner condition on flow state in the case of isotropic flow ($K_y = K_x$).

Fig.10 - Velocity vectors calculated to consider the effect of corner condition on flow state in the case of anisotropic flow ($K_y/K_x = 3.0$).

Experimental Analyses

To check the validity of the numerical solutions, the experimental analyses were carried out on the above systems and the comparison was made on both the results.

Experimental Procedure

Schematic drawing of the die set for experiment is shown in Fig. 11, where ① is the heater to harden the composite materials, ② is the mold, ③ is the die, R_f denotes the corner radius, h denotes the height of the rib and B_0 denotes the width of the rib, respectively. The measurements were performed on the following dimensions: R_f ; 0 and 6 mm, h ; 12, 24 and 36 mm, B_0 ; 30 mm.

Plasticine and BMC which includes 1/4" fibers in length were used experimental materials, and the flow state of BMC as the composite materials was compared with that of plasticine which is known to show a similar behavior at at room temperature to iron and steel placed in hot working process.

In BMC, glass fibers which are randomly oriented at the initial state, orient in the flow direction as the press working proceeds until the thickness of each lamina in the specimen attains to a definite value. Thus the fiber orientation in BMC is unsteady during the process. Therefore, in order to prepare the specimen with the fibers oriented initially in the flow direction, BMC was prepressed from 20 to 6 mm so that the flow might show the anisotropic nature when the molding process was undertaken. The experimental data obtained for the material prepressed in this manner (18 x 134 x 100) were compared with the numerical results.

In order to characterize the flow properties of plasticine and BMC, linear colored marks made of the same material were buried in each lamina at a definite interval and the finite displacement vectors were obtained by measuring the location of marks before and after the molding process. The displacement was analyzed on the three steps of the molding designated by R1, R2 and R3, where the length of rib were taken to be 12 mm, 24 mm and 36 mm for the each step, respectively. In this process for BMC, the velocity of the press stroke and molding temperature were 0.3 mm/s and 135 ~ 140 °C, respectively.

Fig.11 - Die set for experiment.

Experimental Results

In Figs. 12 to 23 are shown the experimentally determined finite displacement vectors, where only the half of the canal are given because of its bisymmetry. Figs. 12 to 17 are of the plasticine flow whereas Figs. 18 to 23 are of the BMC flow. Figs. 12 to 14 and Figs. 18 to 20 are of the case where the corner radius of the die, $R_f = 0$ mm, while Figs. 15 to 17 and Figs. 21 to 23 are of the case where $R_f = 6$ mm. As for the step of the molding process, Figs. 12, 15, 18 and 21 are of the step R1, Figs. 13, 16, 19 and 22 the step R2 and Figs. 14, 17, 20 and 23 the step R3.

From these figures, it can be seen that the flow state of plasticine is comparatively gentle along the canal on the whole and tends to come into the center of rib part, while that of BMC meanders through the corner in the rib canal. It can also be seen that with increasing the value of the center radius, R_f , both the tendencies that the plasticine flow trends toward the center in the rib part through the die corner and that the BMC flow meanders in the rib canal are slightly enhanced.

Discussion

The validity of the model of BMC flow on which the calculations were made as an anisotropic pseudo-plastic material taking into consideration the difference between fluid resistance in normal direction to the flow and in parallel direction has been discussed by comparing with the experimental results. On this base, the actual flow state in the canal with the ribbed boss and the design for the molding system, have been considered.

In the initial flow state, numerical results given in Figs. 4 to 6 are in good agreement with the experimental results given in Figs. 12, 15, 18 and 21; in the case of the isotropic flow, the flow states are gentle on the whole and tend to come to the center in the rib part, and in the case of the anisotropic flow, the flow states have a tendency to meander through the rib canal. These results indicate that the numerical models derived to analyze such the canal and the material may be sufficiently useful to describe the shrinkage and the anisotropic flow state. However, it seems they are still unable to explain the corner condition at the entrance of rib.

When the canal with the corner condition at the entrance of rib (Figs. 2 and 3) are used to analyze the corner condition, the anisotropic constants, K_t , the fluid resistance in normal direction to the flow and K_1 , the one in parallel direction, are, in accordance with the flow direction, transformed into K_x and K_y which are the fluid resistance in the x and y direction, respectively.

The corresponding numerical results that are given in Figs. 7 to 10 show that all the flow states are gentle. However, it should be noted that the flow state of the anisotropic fluid slightly tends to flow along the horizontal direction in the upper part surrounding the symmetric interface in the rib inlet (Figs. 8 and 10) and that the turbulent flow is slightly formed around the corner wall of the die (Fig. 10). The tendency to flow along the horizontal direction is considered to reduce the shrinkage produced in the opposite side against the high convex part with thin wall. Also the turbulent flow assumably reduces the brittle weakness in the bottom part of the fin portion.

The above considerations are based on the comparison of the experimental and numerical results. However, it should be noted that the characteristics of the actual flow state are normalized and weakened by transformation of the pseudo-plastic viscosity on local coordinate into the one on space coordinate.

Fig.12 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R1 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.13 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R2 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.14 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R3 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.15 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R1 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Fig.16 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R2 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Fig.17 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of plasticine flow, R3 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Fig.18 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R1 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.19 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R2 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.20 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R3 step and $R_f = 0$ mm.

Fig.21 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R1 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Fig.22 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R2 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Fig.23 - Finite displacement vectors in the case of BMC flow, R3 step and $R_f = 6$ mm.

Therefore, for more strict treatment, the transformation procedure should be improved to analyze the curved canal.

The tendency of the flow towards the center seen in Figs. 12 to 17 and that of the meander flow seen in Figs. 18 to 23 were not observed in Figs. 7 to 10. This is presumably due to that the governing equations of the steady flow in Eulerian formulation were applied for the analysis.

The present results may, in addition, provide an useful knowledge about the design of die. The trouble of shrinkage in the metal forming is known to be removed by using the die with smaller corner radius. However, when this device is applied to the molding of composite materials such as BMC, the brittle weakness occurs in the bottom part of the fin. From the results given above we conclude that for the molding process of the composite materials using the die with smaller corner radius stronger anisotropic materials such as SMC and prepressed BMC should be used rather than untreated BMC.

Conclusion

The flow state of the composite materials during the molding process was numerically analyzed by assuming the anisotropy for the flow. In the analysis of the initial flow state the numerical results were found to be in good agreement with the experimental results. In the case of canal with the rib, though the anisotropic flow was normalized and weakened by the transformation of the material constants at the calculation, the troubles occurring in the molding process such as the shrinkage and the brittle weakness could be, to a certain extent, explained by the numerical solutions derived on the models constructed. From these results it was concluded that the materials with stronger anisotropy should be used for the molding process of the composite materials.

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